

SPECIALIZED EDUCATIONAL SERVICE (AEE): FACEBOOK SOCIAL NETWORK AS A POSSIBLE EDUCATIONAL SPACE FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS WITH INTELLECTUAL DISABILITIES

ATENCIÓN EDUCATIVA ESPECIALIZADA (AEE): LA RED SOCIAL FACEBOOK COMO POSIBILIDAD DE ESPACIO EDUCATIVO PARA EL DESARROLLO DE ESTUDIANTES CON DISCAPACIDAD INTELECTUAL

ATENDIMENTO EDUCACIONAL ESPECIALIZADO (AEE): A REDE SOCIAL FACEBOOK COMO POSSIBILIDADE DE ESPAÇO EDUCATIVO PARA O DESENVOLVIMENTO DE ESTUDANTES COM DEFICIÊNCIA INTELECTUAL

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Abstract

Technological innovations facilitated by digital networking characterize contemporary society, posing both great challenges and necessary resources for current pedagogical practice. The aim of this study was to analyze the use of the Facebook social network as a potential educational space for the development of students with intellectual disabilities enrolled in the final years of Elementary School (EF), particularly during the interventions carried out in Multifunctional Resource Rooms (MRR). The analysis was conducted through a bibliographic research, and the results indicated that it is possible to utilize Facebook as an educational space, provided that the rules for its use are observed, such as the minimum age of 13 for users, along with the requirement of documents authorizing the students' presence in this space. It also necessitates planning that aligns with the reality of the individuals involved, particularly concerning the availability of technological supports. It is important to highlight that this research was conducted during the year 2022³. The authors who informed this study include: ALENCAR, 2016; BAKHTIN, 2014; BRAUN, 2011; DIAS, 2013; LAKATOS and MARCONI, 2001; LÉVY, 2000; LIMA and PLETSCH, 2018; MANTOAN, 2003; MIRANDA, 2014; MORIN, 2014; MOSCARDINI, 2011; OLIVEIRA, 2018; PLETSCH, 2014; PLETSCH and GLAT, 2012.

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Keywords: Teaching-learning process; multimedia teaching; Facebook; Multifunctional resource rooms; Students with disabilities

Resumen

Las innovaciones tecnológicas posibilitadas por lo digital en red caracterizan la sociedad contemporánea, presentándose como un gran desafío y, al mismo tiempo, como recursos necesarios para la práctica pedagógica en la actualidad. El estudio realizado tuvo como objetivo general analizar el uso de la red social Facebook como posibilidad de espacio educativo para el desarrollo de alumnos con Discapacidad Intelectual matriculados en los últimos años de la Educación Primaria-EF, principalmente durante las atenciones realizadas en las Aulas de Recursos Multifuncionales (ARM). El análisis fue desarrollado a través de una investigación bibliográfica y, según los resultados, se percibió que es posible utilizar la red social Facebook como espacio educativo, siempre y cuando se observen las normas para su uso, como por ejemplo, la edad mínima de 13 años de los usuarios, además de exigir documentos que autoricen la presencia de los estudiantes en este espacio, realizando una planificación acorde a la realidad de las personas involucradas, principalmente en lo que respecta a la disponibilidad de los soportes tecnológicos. Es importante destacar que esta investigación se realizó durante el año 2022. Entre los autores que fundamentaron este trabajo, se destacan: ALENCAR, 2016; BAKHTIN, 2014; BRAUN, 2011; DIAS, 2013; LAKATOS y MARCONI, 2001; LÉVY, 2000; LIMA y PLETSCH, 2018; MANTOAN, 2003; MIRANDA, 2014; MORIN, 2014; MOSCARDINI, 2011; OLIVEIRA, 2018; PLETSCH, 2014; PLETSCH y GLAT, 2012.

Palabras clave: Proceso de enseñanza-aprendizaje; Enseñanza por medios múltiples; Facebook; Aulas de recursos multifuncionales; Educación de estudiantes con discapacidad.

Resumo

Inovações tecnológicas possibilitadas pelo digital em rede caracterizam a sociedade contemporânea, apresentam-se como um grande desafio e, ao mesmo tempo, são recursos necessários para a prática pedagógica na atualidade. O estudo realizado teve como objetivo geral analisar o uso da rede social Facebook como possibilidade de espaço educativo para o desenvolvimento de alunos com Deficiência Intelectual matriculados nos anos finais do Ensino Fundamental-EF, principalmente durante os atendimentos realizados nas Salas de Recursos Multifuncionais (SRM). A análise foi desenvolvida por meio de uma pesquisa bibliográfica e, segundo os resultados, percebeu-se que é possível utilizar a rede social Facebook como espaço educativo, desde que sejam observadas as normas para o seu uso, como, por exemplo, a idade mínima de 13 anos dos usuários, além de exigir documentos que autorizem a presença dos estudantes nesse espaço, realizando um planejamento consoante à realidade das pessoas envolvidas, principalmente no que tange à disponibilidade dos suportes tecnológicos. É importante destacar que essa pesquisa foi realizada durante o ano de 2022. Dentre os autores que embasaram esse trabalho, destacam-se: ALENCAR, 2016; BAKHTIN, 2014; BRAUN, 2011; DIAS, 2013; LAKATOS e MARCONI, 2001; LÉVY, 2000; LIMA e PLETSCH, 2018; MANTOAN, 2003; MIRANDA, 2014; MORIN, 2014; MOSCARDINI, 2011; OLIVEIRA, 2018; PLETSCH, 2014; PLETSCH e GLAT, 2012.

Palavras-chave: Processo de ensino-aprendizagem; Ensino por multimeios; Facebook; Salas de recursos multifuncionais; Educando com deficiência.

Introduction

School is a collective space for learning, a place of appropriation of the culture produced by humanity, a culture that is currently permeated by the presence of New Digital Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs). School is a place for people of all kinds, with diverse ways of being and presenting themselves. School is a place to learn, but to learn much beyond the content and the formal curriculum. Likewise, digital spaces, represented here by the Facebook social network (FB), are places of virtual encounters of people driven by the same interests or who wish to learn new things that are generally not part of the school curriculum, or just to find friends through a search on the FB social network using name, email, or phone, friends who, even geographically distant, come back to interact, now virtually.

Families separated by distance can follow real-time events on the FB social network, such as the birth of a new family member, wedding, birthday, among others. On the FB social network, it is possible to find various pages of artists, singers, writers, painters, pages of NGOs, associations. There are also surname pages, where people end up finding other family members, other generations, sometimes even strangers. Not to mention the pages where events can be scheduled, remote or in-person meetings; pages for those who love animals, nature, cooking, fashion; pages and profiles for sales, exchanges, shops, and general services. In short, on FB, there is a wide variety of options. It is possible to find someone on FB who sells, for example, homemade guava paste, very close to the house of someone who did the search and wants to buy.

In addition to all this, it is also possible to publish photographic memories through albums organized by events with titles and descriptions, publish a thought, a question, a doubt, a written production, in image or video. FB functions as a type of open virtual diary that can be public (accessible to all FB users), private (only you or someone with your password can access it), or with the option to choose that only a group of people have access to the publications.

It is important to note that the minimum age for using Facebook is 13 years old, as established by the platform's Terms of Service. This age restriction is defined by the Children's Online Privacy Protection Rule (COPPA) in the United States. Facebook has a legal obligation to comply with COPPA, which prohibits the collection of personal information from children under 13 years old without parental consent (USA, 2013). In this context, the age range for enrollment in the final years of elementary school is 11 to 14 years old (BRAZIL, 2012). Therefore, this study could only be conducted with students in this stage of education.

To sign up for Facebook, users must provide personal information such as name, date of birth, and email address, among other data. However, just like in face-to-face life, the risks associated with its use should never be ignored, including the virtual presence of strangers, risks of virtual crimes such as offenses, various types of malicious behavior, and exposure of personal data. For this reason, there is the most recent law on cybercrimes, Law No. 14,155/2021 (BRAZIL, 2021), which establishes harsher penalties for cybercrimes. However, it is necessary to take advantage of all the learning and leisure opportunities generated by the exchange among users.

In the technological field, the recent moment generated by the pandemic crisis (COVID-19), widely publicized in the last three years and still not overcome today, has brought the pedagogical practice closer than ever to these digital supports and new technologies. However, it is valid to assert that being close does not always mean understanding or mastering.

Not only schools have been affected, but also many companies have had to change their way of offering services. Transformations have been observed in cinema, TV, and the way people gather and relate to each other. This observation points to the paradoxical fact that "in many schools, there are still closed laboratories, as there is a fear that something may be damaged by their use" (PESSOA; MACHADO, 2019, p. 8). Perhaps this is the moment to review the tools, technological resources, and the way they are dealt with, and this also seems to be the moment to think about the importance of ongoing training that prepares professionals for the use of these resources in practice.

Considering that Information and Communication Technologies - ICTs are not just cell phones, tablets, and computers, it is necessary, nowadays, to mainly understand the remarks about the WEB made by Nobre and Mallmann (2017, p. 3): "Web 1.0 laid the groundwork for a new form of content, the interactive digital 'click.' Web 2.0 introduced online education, socialization tools in networks, and Web 3.0 allowed the creation of e-learning, e-commerce." Regarding what Web 4.0 is, Regina Candida Führ writes the following: "The 4.0 Revolution results in transformation in three axes: Physical Category (autonomous vehicles, 3D printing, advanced robotics), Digital Category, and Biological Category, generating significant impacts on society" (FÜHR, 2018, p. 189).

In other words, modern society is immersed in this era of Web 4.0. However, it is necessary for people to understand that there are also risks and seek ways to protect their privacy and the security of their data. And for its use, it is important to remember that public policies for accessing these means are necessary, as well as specific training for professionals who aim to explore these spaces in search of resources that contribute to their practice, especially in regular classrooms and Multifunctional Resource Rooms.

Methodology

The research methodology used was bibliographic research, which is a research method that involves the analysis and critical evaluation of relevant bibliographic sources on a specific topic. This research method is used in various fields of knowledge, including scientific research, literary production, among others. Bibliographic research involves the search and analysis of bibliographic sources such as books, articles, journals, dissertations, theses, and other printed or digital materials. According to Gil (2010, p. 26), bibliographic research "is developed based on material already prepared, mainly books and scientific articles".

The author emphasizes that this research methodology is suitable for conducting exploratory studies, which aim to "provide greater familiarity with the problem" and "obtain general information" about the research topic. According to Lakatos and Marconi (2001, p. 172), bibliographic research "is not limited to the survey of already

known information" but also "allows the formulation of new problems" and "contributes to the interpretation of results obtained in other research." According to the authors, bibliographic research is a fundamental research methodology in all fields of knowledge because it allows researchers to "acquaint themselves with the scientific production on a particular subject" and "identify the theoretical currents that have been developed" (LAKATOS; MARCONI, 2001, p. 172).

Facebook and People with Intellectual Disabilities

Just like all individuals who end up being involved and affected by the use of new technologies, schools, and Specialized Educational Assistance (SEA) provided in the Multifunctional Resource Room (MRR) could not be left out. Throughout her professional career, the researching teacher observed that students showed a lot of interest in using computers, tablets, and cellphones, rather than engaging in activities using printed sheets, board games, and other dynamics. They frequently requested the teacher to turn on the computer or lend them a cellphone, even if it was only at the end of each session.

Furthermore, it was also noticeable that the research conducted by these students on cellphones and/or computers always involved searches on the YouTube platform (searching for cartoons, videos with specific themes, music) or on the Facebook page (searching for relatives and friends, photographs, memes).

This observation motivated the writing of this work, which has as its central problem the fact that these students, most of whom have Intellectual Disabilities (ID), even those with significant cognitive limitations, showed little interest in activities related to reading, games, painting, among others, when compared to their interest in accessing the internet or handling technological devices. Some of them had great ease in accessing data and expressing their interests, especially on the social media platforms Facebook and YouTube. Many of them, still in the process of literacy, used voice commands or typed one or two letters of the alphabet in the search bar, hoping that the results (suggestions) would appear so that they could identify what they were looking for through images.

Many times, the students navigated through the material found in the suggestions that appeared within a few seconds and shifted their focus from the initial research, as if navigating in a sea of possibilities, and the cellphone or the computer became the boats that took them on this adventure of exploring and discovering new things. It was also noticed that these same students had difficulty interpreting and attributing meaning to the symbols present in the school environment, difficulties in communication, and apparent lack of interest in learning, especially in regular classrooms, which directly interfered with the acquisition of specific skills for their grade level.

According to the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM), which was published by the American Psychiatric Association (APA) (2014, p. 14), intellectual disability "falls under the neurodevelopmental disorders and has four levels of severity: mild (F70), moderate (F71), severe (F72), and profound (F73)." Regarding the conditions of neurodevelopmental disorders and their main characteristics, it can be said that these disorders;

[...] manifest early in development, typically before the child enters school, and are characterized by deficits in development that result in impairments in personal, social, academic, or occupational functioning. Developmental deficits range from very specific limitations in learning or executive functioning to global impairments in social skills or intelligence [...]. (APA, 2014, p. 72).

Studies point out the possibilities of working with students with intellectual disabilities, global developmental disorders, and high abilities/giftedness, among other disabilities, and highlight: "There is evidence that living only in segregated environments does not promote and stimulate their comprehensive development in the same way as inclusive educational environments" (OLHER; GUILHOTO, 2013, p. 5). And in these environments, where everyone learns together, these students have opportunities that are denied to them in segregated settings. Therefore, "[...] both the experience in the regular classroom and the complementary work in the regular education system enhance the development of these students" (OLHER; GUILHOTO, 2013, p.5).

In this sense, it is necessary to consider individuality when planning and, especially in the classroom, think about strategies that address different methodologies and resources because, regardless of the degree of disability and its biological or social origin, "[...] there is a spectrum of severity, but it does not invalidate the purpose of inclusion, which requires specific actions and short, medium, and long-term planning" (OLHER; GUILHOTO, 2013, p. 4). The use of differentiated resources and strategies in curricular practices through coordinated planning with the general curriculum is essential and, in many cases, indispensable, considering that "biology is not determinant in an individual's development, but their relationship with the social and cultural aspects that offer numerous possibilities to overcome difficulties" (DIAS; OLIVEIRA, 2013, p. 6). In this path, regarding education and inclusion, Pletsch (2014) emphasizes that:

The debate on the flexibility and individualization of the curriculum for students with special educational needs, particularly those with intellectual disabilities, involves recognizing their specificities in internalizing culture through different social and psychological tools. Moreover, recognizing individuality should be the guiding principle of curricular practices for any student, as an education that aims to be humanistic cannot be based on "Fordist" curriculum assumptions (PLETSCH, 2014, p. 13).

It is believed that research on the subject is extremely necessary in the current context of an increasingly connected society. Furthermore, it is necessary to seek strategies for students with Intellectual Disabilities to have access to knowledge based on the studied school content. In other words, to ensure their right to learning.

Some data on previous studies on the topic

The researcher conducted a survey, between the twenty-fifth (25th) and twenty-eighth (28th) of May in two thousand and twenty-one (2021), on Google Scholar, regarding existing studies addressing the same topic to assess the relevance of her own study. Considering only the titles of the works and based on data collected from works presented specifically in the Portuguese language, the results were as follows:

- First search using the phrase "Intellectual Disability": approximately two hundred and seventy-four thousand (274,000) results.
- Second search using the phrase "Facebook social network": approximately seventy-one thousand eight hundred (71,800) results.
- Third search using the phrase "Multifunctional Resource Rooms": approximately twenty-three thousand seven hundred (23,700) results.

Next, it can be observed that when conducting a more comprehensive search closer to the theme of this study, the results decrease in terms of the number of published works:

- 1 Fourth search using the phrase "Intellectual Disability and reading skills": approximately ten thousand one hundred (10,100) results.
- 2 Fifth search using the phrase "Intellectual Disability and Multifunctional Resource Rooms": approximately thirteen thousand nine hundred (13,900) results.
- 3 Sixth search using the phrase "Facebook social network in Multifunctional Resource Rooms": approximately two thousand seven hundred thirty (2,730) results.

When the title of this research was used in its entirety, it generated approximately eight thousand eight hundred eighty (8,880) results. Upon analyzing the results of the titles, it was noticed that no work found presented all aspects of the research together. They were either about Intellectual Disability and resource rooms or about Facebook as an educational space.

It was also observed that the results narrow down as they get closer to the research topic. However, several works, articles, and books brought valuable contributions; some of them were found in the case study titled "Facebook as a technology supportive of multiliteracies for students with intellectual disability: a case study" written by Mayssara Reany de Jesus Oliveira (2015) and used as a prerequisite to obtain her specialist title in literacies and interdisciplinary practices. In it, the author discusses the notions of intellectual disability, the contributions of multimodal genres, which are distinct forms of text presentation on the social network, and how these genres establish virtual communication and interaction, potentially enabling

multiliteracy. According to Francisco (2018, p. 3), "the concept of communicative multiliteracies was developed to expand traditional approaches to literacies that initially focused their studies on processes involving only written texts".

In this context, works such as those by Lucena (2016), Alencar (2016), and Miranda (2014), among others, were also found, addressing the use of the Facebook social network as an educommunicative tool, the interweaving of friendship relationships with curricula between networks, and Facebook as a pedagogical resource in the learning of students with disabilities. These works demonstrate the possibility of the pedagogical use of the Facebook social network by people with disabilities and highlight that many studies are being conducted in search of technological inclusion that contributes to access to school knowledge.

The referenced works present the difficulties encountered as well as significant interaction and learning processes, considering that "the determining factor is not the technology itself. What enhances practices are the uses made of the equipment or artifacts and the agency performed by the practicing subjects of these everyday practices" (LUCENA, 2016, p. 120). However, they do not show how access to school knowledge can occur in the virtual environment for students with intellectual disabilities. Therefore, it is believed that this research can contribute precisely by helping to answer that question, adding to everything that has been researched in the field.

Specialized Educational Assistance (SEA)

The guidelines for Specialized Educational Assistance (SEA) in Basic Education are established by Resolution No. 4/2009, from the National Council of Education, the Chamber of Basic Education (BRAZIL, 2009). Article 2 of this Resolution clarifies that the function of SEA is to complement or supplement the student's education by providing services, accessibility resources, and strategies that eliminate barriers to their full participation in society and their learning development. Braun and Vianna (2011, p. 3) assert that Specialized Educational

Assistance is intended to ensure the student's continued enrollment in regular school, first by providing access to the curriculum through physical accessibility, such as architectural adaptations, transportation services, furniture and equipment adjustments, and access to communication systems. As a result of this access, SEA also aims to facilitate the organization of didactic and pedagogical materials, differentiated strategies, and appropriate assessment instruments tailored to the student's needs, so that their presence in school truly fosters academic and personal development.

For many years, students with disabilities, Global Developmental Disorders (GDD), and high abilities/giftedness were only quantitatively present in schools. It was only in the 1990s that the focus on this population began to change. Public policy frameworks began to be altered as a result of international discussions⁴, which influenced the creation of national public policies⁵ such as the Guidelines and Bases of National Education Law (LDB) No. 9394/96 (BRAZIL, 1996), published in 2008 by the Ministry of Education, which states in Article 54: "Special Education, for the purposes of this Law, is understood as a modality of school education preferably offered in regular education networks, aimed at students with disabilities, global developmental disorders, and high abilities or giftedness." The same Article 54 also mentions the "National Policy on Special Education in the Perspective of Inclusive Education" (BRAZIL, 2008).

This document began to guide the organization and operation of Special Education in Brazilian educational systems and is based on Education for diversity, understanding Special Education as a "teaching modality that permeates all levels, stages, and modalities, provides specialized educational assistance, makes resources and services available, and provides guidance on their use in the teaching and learning process" (BRAZIL, 2008, p. 16).

Regarding specialized educational assistance, the document states that it "identifies, develops, and organizes pedagogical and accessibility resources that eliminate barriers to the full participation of students, considering their specific needs" (BRAZIL, 2008, p.16). In the Multifunctional Resource Room (MRR), SEA allows for a

⁴ International public policies: World Declaration on Education for All (1990); Salamanca Declaration (1994); Guatemala Convention (1999), among others.

⁵ National public policies: Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education - Law nº 9.394/96; National Education Plan - PNE; Law No. 10,172/2001, among others.

more individualized encounter with the student, due to its complementary and supplementary objective of promoting autonomy within and outside the school (BRAZIL, 2008). Therefore, professionals working in SEA have the opportunity to identify individual characteristics more easily, as they are not faced with overcrowded classrooms, and they also have the possibility of collaborating with other school professionals, especially with the regular classroom teachers of students enrolled in SEA and served in the MRR during off-hours.

Reflecting on pedagogical work, Moscardini (2011) states that the SEA teacher should also promote diversified activities because, in order to promote access to knowledge, these activities should go beyond repetition and stimulate the construction of concepts and abstractions necessary for the development of complex thinking functions mentioned earlier. Collaborative work becomes equally essential so that regular classroom teachers, teachers working in the MRR, and the entire school team can engage in dialogue and collectively establish their work and learning objectives because "The absence of dialogue between regular education teachers and teachers in the Multifunctional Resource Room hinders any joint work proposal" (MASCARDINI, 2011, p.140).

Regarding SEA and the historical and cultural dimension of intellectual disabilities, the mediating role of the teacher is irreplaceable, not only due to their experience but also their qualifications. This mediation can lead students to higher levels of functioning (SÃO PAULO, 2012). Students need many moments of intentional pedagogical mediation for them to have fewer difficulties, improve their abilities, and enhance their educational and social development (LIMA; PLETSCH, 2018).

Therefore, according to Pletsch and Glat (2012, p.12), "the focus needs to shift from learning difficulties as an intrinsic problem of the student to understanding them as a result of social and pedagogical interactions established in the classroom." It is necessary for teachers to have prior knowledge of the specific demands and realities of each student since, even in the complexity of the classroom, students with intellectual disabilities have more possibilities to expand their abilities and improve their educational development by occupying these spaces.

To achieve the inclusion of students with disabilities, it is necessary to think of strategies that bridge the gap between theory and practice, considering that public policies exist, but sometimes there is a lack of objective conditions to materialize those policies. Planning and systematization of the reference content to be taught are necessary to bridge the gap between theory and practice. This may be the crux of all the issues that educators grapple with daily because, as Pletsch (2014, p. 18) states, "[..] it seems to us that the proclaimed education in so-called inclusive schools is still not for everyone. Furthermore, specialized support during off-hours is insufficient or precarious".

However, believing in paradigm shifts makes teaching work worthwhile. Believing that it is possible, in everyday life, to design and find new paths to access knowledge is the essence of education. There is no doubt that "we have in our hands the protagonism of action, pressing for change, demanding that legislation be enforced, occupying empty spaces, and through gaps, finding paths" (OLIVEIRA, 2018, p. 63).

Possibilities of new educational spaces: Facebook as a resource for the development of individuals with intellectual disabilities.

Regarding the technological movement, it has occurred and continues to occur in society; first, outside of schools, and as mentioned by Romero and Souza (2008, p. 2), "if schools feel surprised by it today, it is because they did not perceive or keep up with the social changes that generated it. Meanwhile, some countries are already discussing a fourth paradigm." Regarding this subject, Mantoan (2003, p. 11) states that "it is undeniable that the old paradigms of modernity are being questioned, and knowledge, the raw material of school education, is undergoing reinterpretation".

In this scenario, with the presence of ICTs, we have social networks and their various possibilities, such as interacting with people who are physically far away, in other countries and continents, having access to content posted by individuals in a group or page, reading diverse opinions, and even sharing one's own experiences.

However, the purpose of this work is not to evaluate what is right or wrong, but to analyze the use of Facebook as a possibility for an educational space for the development of students with intellectual disabilities. What reason would justify not using it for learning purposes? Isn't the social network currently another valuable tool in favor of teachers? It is possible to assert that "inevitably, the new network culture extends to the education system" (MOREIRA; JANUÁRIO, 2014, p. 74). According to the authors:

Social networks, collective and collaborative spaces for communication and information exchange, can facilitate the creation and development of communities of practice or learning, provided there is an explicit educational intentionality. These virtual communities have emerged as an important alternative to traditional learning and organizational contexts and, when supported by technologies, have become more visible today (MOREIRA; JANUÁRIO, 2014, p.75).

The social network Facebook is one of the most widely used services by the population and offers various possibilities for interactivity, posting, sharing, and reaction buttons such as like, love, and sad, which allow users not only to express their opinions but also to interact with the posts of other users (SANTOS; ROSSINI, 2014). There are many possibilities generated by the technological revolution and the opportunities it can offer to those who are engaging in networking. Special Education cannot be left out of the discoveries and studies in this field. Regarding the creation of Facebook, Arrington (2005), cited by Amante (2014), states:

Created in 2004 by a group of young Harvard university students (Mark Zuckerberg, Dustin Moskovitz, Eduardo Saverin, and Chris Hughes), it aimed to create a space where people could meet, share opinions and photographs, initially intending to build a communication network solely for the university students. However, within a few months, the network expanded among American universities, connecting young people from over 800 institutions (ARRINGTON, 2005, cited in AMANTE, 2014, p. 30).

Therefore, this phenomenon, once used for pedagogical purposes, considering the increasing number of an increasingly connected population, must be observed, studied, and its uses documented. The qualitative data of these accesses and the presence of people in this environment should not be disregarded, as this seems to be

a contemporary pedagogical emergency. It is worth noting here that "Education and communication as areas of knowledge flow and update according to the opportunities offered by the most diverse technological innovations" (VALENTE, 2014, p.2). As an example, we observe what the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC) states:

Human activities are carried out in social practices, mediated by different languages: verbal (oral or visual-motor, such as Libras, and written), bodily, visual, auditory, and, contemporarily, digital. Through these practices, people interact with themselves and others, constituting themselves as social subjects. In these interactions, knowledge, attitudes, and cultural, moral, and ethical values are intertwined (BRASIL, 2018, p. 65).

Regarding language, it functions as a mechanism of dialogue, constant movement, and transformation, "always carrying content or experiential meaning" (BAKHTIN, 2014, p. 99). The author understands language as the product of social construction and expression of experiences, resulting from human interaction, arising from dialogue. In the present day, human interaction, historically carried out in a face-to-face manner, also takes place in virtual space. Furthermore, the social network does not need to replace face-to-face work but can be used as a tool in schools, both in Multifunctional Resource Rooms (SRM) and in regular classrooms, provided that conditions related to devices and connectivity are offered.

With the advent of ICTs and social networks, there is a need to investigate how communication, interaction, and learning occur for students with intellectual disabilities in virtual environments, since today's society, in its historical journey towards inclusion, is still immersed in the theory-practice gap, and the same occurs in the virtual environment, "as digital inclusion is entirely linked to exclusion" (VAZ et al., 2015, p. 3). Considering that this process of technological development is continuous, in the words of Lévy (2000, p.43), "Cyberspace is today the system with the fastest development in the entire history of communication techniques. By dethroning television, it will probably be, from the beginning of the next century, the center of gravity of the new ecology of communications".

And everyone, without distinction, is included on this same planet, they are subjects of the same machinery, driving and being driven from all sides. Still quoting Lévy (2000, p.39), "all the great cities of the planet are like the different neighborhoods of a single virtual megalopolis." And within this megalopolis are people with and without disabilities. Therefore, specific educational problems "must be at the center of concerns in the education of young people who will undoubtedly become citizens" (MORIN, 2001, p.1).

On Facebook, "with a profile and the available basic features, it is possible to build a stimulating learning space" (MOREIRA; JANUARIO, 2014, p.76). It is possible to bring the possibilities offered by this social network into the classroom, as these platforms represent, through their users, intellectual and cultural environments that can facilitate learning while promoting interaction and collaboration. This is the sense of belonging among its members (MOREIRA; JANUARIO, 2014). It is like a virtual living room that brings together groups with common interests, all in any space-time, regardless of distance, time, or economic class, generating relationships that would otherwise not be possible.

It is common knowledge that "Social networks are not a recent phenomenon, nor did they arise with the web; they have always existed in society, motivated by the individuals' need to share knowledge, information, or preferences among themselves" (MOREIRA; JANUARIO, 2014, p. 74). And it is precisely this human need to share that makes the Facebook social network a conducive space for the promotion of knowledge, an educational space that can be explored in a mediated manner through planning and using its tools, utilizing multiple languages.

In which other spaces would this fluidity be possible? This mixture and movement of language, where in certain spaces "the plural is configured when mentioning sign language, music language, visual language. Regarding the latter, one speaks of painting, photography, cinema. There are languages" (PALOMO, 2001, p. 3). Language is part of the human being and is not only presented through verbal means; man and language are inseparable, as they are the manifestation of their social and cultural capabilities (PALOMO, 2001).

In the classroom: paper, pencil, blackboard, chairs arranged in rows indicating that students should face forward. It could be that the teacher reads or tells a story; it could be that the students have the freedom to speak openly after the reading done by the teacher; it could be that they have the opportunity to share their reflections. Classrooms are plural spaces, but texts, words, and writing predominate in them, just as they were seen in the schools of the parents and grandparents of those who are now inside them. As Valente (2014, p. 2) emphasizes, "they still have the same structure and use the same methods used in 19th-century education: curricular activities are still based on pencil and paper, and the teacher still occupies the position of the main protagonist, the holder and transmitter of information".

However, it is undeniable that writing and reading are undergoing transformations brought about by digital technologies; now, the text can be dynamic, have images, have sound, have movement; a new complex language is the change brought about by hypermedia (SANTAELLA, 2007). As the same author aptly expresses:

Thus, hybrid, mixed syntaxes are created. Sounds, words, and images that previously could only coexist now co-generate in fluid structures, liquid cartographies for navigation with which users learn to interact, through participatory actions like in a game. This is the principle of hypermedia, a principle that installs itself at the core of language. Although hypermedia can be configured in supports such as CD-ROM and DVD, today it constitutes itself, without a doubt, in the rhizomatic and infinite language of networks. (SANTAELLA, 2007, p.11).

Given the above in this study, regarding the relationship between human beings and learning in the virtual environment, it is worth noting that technologies and the multiple possibilities generated by the web allow for differentiated and innovative strategies, which include teaching students to think, cooperate, and learn about cyberspace, with Facebook being one of the most widely used social networks in the world (PATRÍCIO; GONÇALVES, 2010). Therefore: "Incorporating social networks into schools seems to us an inevitable step to maintain proximity with our students" (MOREIRA; JANUARIO, 2014, p.69). It is worth highlighting that:

When internalizing instructions, children modify their cognitive operations: perception, attention, memory, problem-solving skills. It is in this way that historically determined and socially organized ways of operating with information influence individual knowledge, self-awareness, and awareness of the world (DAVIS; OLIVEIRA, 1988, p.63).

Some ways in which Facebook can be used as an educational space include:

- Creation of private groups for school classes or students of a particular subject. The group can be used to share resources, discuss, and collaborate on projects.
- Participation in public groups that maintain information about a specific topic. This can serve to learn about a particular subject or connect with other students or professionals in their field of study and interest.

It is believed that these instructions and possibilities can also be found in the social network Facebook and used by teachers in regular classrooms and in Multifunctional Resource Rooms, provided they have prior knowledge, preferably specific training, access to the internet, and access to technological resources. It is thought that the teacher should not disregard the critical aspects of using these tools in the classroom, which should not justify practices that are alien to these technologies.

Conclusion

It is possible to conclude that Facebook can be used as an educational space, but it is important to keep in mind that it was not originally designed for educational purposes. However, it is possible to create private or public groups on the platform to share information, resources, and knowledge. With this, Facebook enables the planning of classes and support services in Specialized Educational Assistance Centers that encourage students to interact and use the various forms of language present in this environment. It allows for individual interest-based searches and the creation of sharing environments with the presentation of information, news, and the study of pages and profiles, as long as the platform's established policies are observed.

Thus, the platform represents a resource that can contribute to the professional practice of teachers, especially those specialized in Specialized Educational Assistance. However, in this context, it is necessary to consider that these professionals must have access to technological devices, internet access, and working conditions that facilitate

the use of these resources, in addition to specific training. Taking these considerations into account, Facebook can offer more possibilities and support that contribute to the success of the teaching and learning process for students with disabilities.

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